

ANALYSIS OF APPROACHES TO THE METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes approaches to the concept and structural structures of the methodological competence of a modern teacher as part of professional pedagogical competence. The methodological competence of a teacher is determined not only by knowledge of teaching methods of his subject, but also by the ability to diagnose his personal characteristics and skills. The methodological competence of a teacher reflects the systemic level of thinking, methodological knowledge and skills acquired in the process of methodological activities. For this reason, the methodological competence of the teacher is focused on ensuring effective and high-quality solutions to pedagogical and methodological problems, taking into account the educational opportunities and needs of students.*

Keywords: *modern educator, psychologist, practical experience, skills*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the implementation of continuous reforms in the educational system of Uzbekistan, it began to expand the field of pedagogical creativity by recognizing educators as the main person of the educational system and freeing them as much as possible from formality, paperwork.

A modern educator is not only a specialist in a particular subject, but also a Methodist, educator, psychologist, as well as a subject of Education who constantly improves his professional skills. That is, he became a kind of "universal person" who perceives new directions of Education, enriches his activities with non-standard solutions, provides flexibility in communicating with children and parents.

Therefore, it is difficult for a modern educator to successfully act on the basis of practical experience, professional and universal knowledge, skills in solving professional problems. This in turn encourages educators to have professional and personal competencies. For example, personal competencies include personal, interpersonal, social, and reflectivity [1].

Among the professional competencies in terms of educational, educational and developmental processes are the following pedagogical competencies; information and communicative competencies (all-intagological and scientific-pedagogical feature); General instrumental competencies in accordance with the state educational standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as psychological-pedagogical, general and scientific competencies.

However, it is a little difficult to demand from educators to respond to the competencies specified in the regulatory documents. The need for formality in the workplace in many cases interferes with this. Basically, it is like working directly with students in the auditorium, communicating with their parents during extracurricular hours, communicating with colleagues [2]

So, today it is much more important to increase the level of professional competence of an educator.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In local and foreign scientific and pedagogical literature, the concept of "professional and pedagogical competence" is usually considered in three: competence-professional competence - professional and pedagogical competence.

For Example, D.A.Ivanov, K.G.Mitrofanov and O.V.Sokolovas characterize competence as an individual's ability to solve certain problems. That is, if it shows the result of solving a particular problem situation, the person can be called competent in a particular area.

In turn, V.A.Slastenin, I.F.Isaev and A.I.The Mishchenko focus on the unity of theoretical and practical training of the educator for the implementation of his activities. Thus, in this case, researchers equate the concept of "competence" with professionalism.

Russian pedagogical scientist N.V.Kuzmina proposes to consider competence from a psychological-pedagogical point of view: competence is the ability to understand oneself and others, to predict interpersonal phenomena.

Foreign scientific opinion is also ambiguous in determining competence. For example, American researchers on this topic in the 1980s V.Blank and D.The Shawnee considered competence to be the ability to carry out activities based on knowledge and thinking in reality.

In the 1990s, foreign pedagogical scientist F.Chivelli attributed competence to the main signs of personality: the abilities of a person, his personal characteristics and acquired knowledge, as well as the compliance of the results of specialist activities with professional standards. His colleagues in the United States - specialists from the Ohio State University Center for vocational education and training-understood competence as the exact knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for effective professional activities.

In the early 2000s, British researcher K.Winch proposed that competence should be based on the ability to perform a task according to certain criteria in a particular situation. In terms of content, the concept of "competence" lies on the basis of the term "professional competence".

Local researchers on educational problems O.V.Akulova, V.V.Laptev, A.P.Tryapitsyna and others attribute professional competence to the indispensable quality of a person, characterized by knowledge, education and life experience, the ability to solve professional tasks and problems using values. V.I.Bidenko also emphasizes the connection between professional competence and the personal characteristics of the specialist. Bidenko was supported by N.N.Chridina includes the ability to update existing experience and knowledge to the concept of " professional competence", self-mobilization, as well as a high level of adaptation to changing working conditions.

Currently, most modern local researchers agree that the formation of professional competence occurs only by overcoming professional difficulties, solving problems and finding a way out of the situation [2, 3] et al.

In addition, unique research in this area is presented in the English-language work of Russian researchers published in the journals of the International Information and analytical databases Scopus and Web of Science. So, in the magazine "Espacios" in 2019, N.I.Demkina, P.A.Kostikov and K.A.Lebedev's article on approaches to the development of professional competence of future IT specialists was published. In this work, the authors presented a model of professional competence, which should include advanced methodological complexes that meet the modern requirements of the educational and scientific information environment. In general,

according to the authors, such models must first meet the requirements of the information society [4].

In 2022, an article by the team of authors of the Krasnoyarsk State Pedagogical University was published in the Journal of the Siberian Federal University. V.P.Astafieva (M.G.Yanova, V.V.Janów, S.V.Kravchenko, I.V.Vetrova reveals the essence of the professional competence of the physical education educator.

The scientific direction of foreign research on the development of professional competence largely corresponds to the Russian school. For example, Austrian scholars Elizabeth Windle and Johannes Dammerer highlight the role of mentoring young professionals in the professional adaptation of educators. The development of professional competence of future educators in Bulgaria is noted in the works of researcher Vera Gyurova of Sofia University.

Researchers Mikela Freddano and Valeria Pandolfini of the Italian National Institute for educational assessment in Rome believe that the main component of professional competence is the improvement of the qualifications of specialists of the existing educational system.

METHODS

analysis of historical, retrospective and theoretical-methodological sources, generalization and interpretation of the information received, observation, conversation, questionnaire, content analysis, qualimetry and expert assessment.

METHODOLOGICAL BASE OF THE RESEARCH

There are different types of professional-pedagogical competence: psychological-pedagogical, socio-cultural, methodological, subject, methodological, etc.

A special place among the types of professional pedagogical competence is occupied by methodological competence, since the level of professional competence of an educator depends on it [5].

In local pedagogical knowledge, educators began talking about methodological competence from the second half of the 1990s. At this time, V.I.Zemtsova, N.L.Stefanova, V.A.Adolf, the works of the T.S.Polyakova appeared [6, 7].

This is evidenced by the results of the analysis of the existing scientific literature in the field of pedagogy, in which the methodological competence of the educator is interpreted as follows:

- the value relationship of the pedagogical personality to the pedagogical profession, as well as an integral, professionally significant feature that reflects the sum of professional knowledge and skills (T.V. Syasina);
- a set of methodological knowledge and methodological skills necessary for the implementation of educational and methodological activities, as well as personality qualities of professional importance (T.S.Mamontova);
- the sum of the skills of the educator to master his knowledge of various teaching methods and didactic methods, teaching techniques, psychological mechanisms of acquiring knowledge and skills in the educational process (N.V.Kuzmina);
- integral property of the individual, a complex personal resource that provides the possibility of effective interaction with the outside world in a particular area (R.P.Milrud);
- * an integral description of business, personal and moral qualities of an educator, reflecting a system of methodological, methodological knowledge, qualifications, experience, motivation,

abilities and readiness for creative self-realization in methodological and pedagogical activity (T.A. Zagrivnya);

• I.V. According to Grebnev, it is one of the important components of the professional competence of an educator.

F.F. Nagibin and N.V. Ippolitovs believe that the methodological competence of an educator is based on the sum of psychological and pedagogical, scientific and methodological knowledge, skills, qualifications, skills, motivation and personal qualities necessary for the qualitative implementation of educational and methodological activities.

RESEARCH RESULTS

We tried to study this concept in the process of analyzing the concept of "methodological competence of an educator" based on the positions of various scientists. We were convinced that the definitions of this concept by scientists who studied the "methodological competence of an educator" do not contradict each other, but rather complement each other. In the process of analysis, we witnessed the absence of a single generally accepted definition.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that methodological competence as one of the most important components of professional competence of an educator, due to changes in its content, assumes a revision of its specifics.

Analyzing the content, structure and criteria of the "methodological competence of an educator", we, together with determining the content of this concept, understand it as a structural, integral part of professional competence, professional personality. Hence, the "methodological competence of an educator" is determined by his skill, professional capabilities and needs, reflecting the level of systematic acquisition of methodological knowledge and skills acquired in the process of pedagogical activity, personal qualities aimed at ensuring an effective and qualitative solution of educational and methodological problems [8, 9].

In the process of analyzing the professional activity of an educator, we are guided by N.G. Taking into account the features of the structure of the methodological competence of the educator proposed by Masyukova, we have identified such components as: subject-activity, cognitive, analytical-reflexive, personal and Information Technology.

Pedagogical activity of an educator is traditionally associated with such types of activities as scientific-methodological and psychological-pedagogical. The information stage of the development of society requires a review of Information Technology in the structure of methodological competence [10].

Justification of the importance of the information technology component of methodological competence based on the analysis of regulatory documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1) first, the National Project "Education" is tasked with creating a modern digital educational environment that is safe for educational participants and ensures the openness of education and its high quality;

2) secondly, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on education" No. 637 of September 23, 2020 established important guidelines for the development of education aimed at the implementation of basic general education programs in electronic form and using distance learning technologies, taking into account the fact that educational institutions should ensure the protection of information security and personal data of educational participants;

3) third, according to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 4, 2015 "on the establishment of the Ministry of Information Technology and

communications development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the implementation of measures to ensure information security and the implementation of modern technologies for the protection of communication networks, software products, information systems and resources, further development of technical infra-structure

Information security refers to the protection of information and the infrastructure that supports it from accidental or intentional influences of a natural or artificial nature. Such effects can severely damage information relations, including information owners, information beneficiaries, and the infrastructure that provides information protection. In the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the principles and guarantees of freedom of information" of December 12, 2002, information security is defined as information security and refers to the state of protection of the interests of the individual, society and the state in the field of information.

4) fourth, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved new state educational standards of Primary, general secondary and higher education, which provide the basis for the formation of a person in the conditions of the formation of a modern Information Society for the coming decades. State educational standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the appropriate ICT tools and the adequate qualification level of employees who use and support them, Information Technology and Information Protection,

Oorq-444 of September 8, 2017, states that the protection of children from information harmful to their health should ensure the functioning of the electronic information and educational environment at the level of educational institutions in accordance with OORQ-547 of July 2, 2019. So, based on the analysis of the regulatory documents discussed above, we came to the conclusion that the methodological competence of an educator is based on knowledge in the field of information technology literacy, distance education and information security [11].

CONCLUSION

In general, the analysis of research in the field of methodological competence of an educator made it possible to present the evolution of the development of this problem.

Thus, in foreign and domestic researchers, the concept of "methodological competence" has been studied since the second half of the 1990s, which is necessary not only in the field of teaching methodology of their subjects, but also in pedagogical activity; ladigan also implies the ability to apply knowledge about the achievements of Science and technology in practice.

In general, the methodological concept develops side by side with the terms "professional competence" and "professional-pedagogical competence" of studies in the direction of Labor psychology [12].

The methodological concept of an educator is a competence that allows you to cope with a large number of situations and work in a group, not only in order to have professional competence, but in a broader sense. The presence of a methodological concept in educators serves to raise their activities from flexible and reproductive to an effective and creative level.

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